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HOW TO EMBED 'THE REFLECTIVE ENGINEER' IN HIGHER ENGINEERING EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In 2019, the authors came up with a vision of the future university for engineers. It describes a future situation and behaviour of 'reflective engineers' who interact and behave in a particular way while engaging with technology. The vision is created with a Vision in Product Design (VIP) methodology from Hekkert & van Dijk. This vision of the future university starts with the idea that every one of us has personal ambitions, talents and interests that drives our interests and ways of working for the good of society at large. Nevertheless, at the start of our career, we may not be aware of these ambitions, talents and interests, and one needs to explore and reflect on a variety of challenges to discover:

- (1) In what way we would like to engage with technology
- (2) How would we like to work together in the technological domain
- (3) Whether we prefer to engage in slow/fast production cycles

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A reflective portfolio including engineering roles as a vehicle to become a deliberate professional will be embedded in the interdisciplinary master curriculum of biomedical engineering at the 3ME department at TU Delft. In this conceptual paper, we will expand on the design implementation process of the reflective engineer in challenge-based education following the vision of the future university.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In the future, we expect students to want to engage either by addressing societal needs or unravel a phenomenon, to collaborate based on trust exploring new fields or within a system and last but not least, to work on short projects or long term projects. Each of these dimensions requires a different engineering role to be enacted and, most importantly, continuous reflection on whom we want to become as a person and as an engineer [1].

This process does not stop after “formal” education stops but is a lifelong and ongoing activity, which requires technee’s (life longer learners) to reflect on their personal, professional and ethical development across different engineering themes from different role perspectives. Becoming a deliberate professional as defined by Trede [2] requires the technee to (1) question their assumptions and (re)consider their place in the world. (2) Learn to think and act critically for themselves and being responsible for their choices (3) and use critical thinking as a tool to think beyond their discipline, culture, policies and develop moral /non -categorical thinking capabilities [2].

1.2 DELIBERATE PROFESSIONAL

This Deliberate professional is a concept introduced by Trede [2] in her book on the transition of HE students into becoming a professional. The book considers the complexity of practices, workplace cultures and environments and states that students in the transition phase from master student to professional need to;

- (1) understand what is probable, possible and impossible concerning existing and changing practices;
- (2) take a deliberate stance in positioning oneself in practice as well as in making technical decisions;
- (3) be aware of and responsible for the consequences of actions taken or actions not taken in relation to the ‘doing’, ‘saying’, ‘knowing’ and ‘relating’ in practice; and
- (4) be aware of the multiple agencies one has to acquire to exercise free will, innovate, act on prescribed roles, and focus on long-term goals across various domains.

As we are implementing the vision of the future university, we try to integrate the deliberate professional model with the faculty’s ambitions to grow reflective engineers by challenge-based education.

1.3 VISION OF THE FUTURE UNIVERSITY

The Vision of the University of the future is shaped around a curriculum in which **basic** fundamental knowledge is addressed derived from particular disciplines or themes with an epistemological knowledge base. This fundamental knowledge allows students to identify and evaluate the probable and the (im)possible in ongoing practice. What basic knowledge do I need is the critical question? In this case, the

implementation is taking place in the Biomedical field but could be addressed in any engineering domain.

Fig. 1 Reflective Engineering Model

At the next level, **Institutional** knowledge is applied in a particular context, which requires generic methods and tools to work in (1) systems or interpersonal settings, in (2) short and long production cycles and on (3) knowledge focused on phenomena or societal needs. Naturally, these generic methods and tools should be applied in a thematic (sub)domain ((inter)discipline). Which methods/tools/collaborative ways of working are used for my area of interest is the critical question.

As a result of these dimensions, **Engineering Roles** are emerging. Due to the active agency of the technee to do or to stop certain activities, specific behaviour will become more or less prominent. This level mainly requires transferable skills, such as creative thinking or leadership, attributes of behaviour in a specific context and agency based on values related to ethics and sustainability, amongst others. Ultimately, the Engineering Roles will be guiding roles on how a technee wants to operate in the future technical domain. Whom do I want to be and which behaviours basic, institutional, transferable, and interpersonal level belong to my role is the crucial question.

Ideally, these different levels of knowledge creation are practised and experienced in a challenge-based education environment where students can enact appropriate and professional behaviour, feedback and reflection are needed to become a deliberate professional engineer who contributes to different knowledge systems in society. What professional behaviour is expected of me? (values, culture, attitude, and how does it fit my Eng. Role?)

Even though these knowledge levels are related sequentially, they will be taking place in parallel and need proper guidance and facilitation. The connections between the levels of knowledge building include iterative moments of reflection, formative 360 % assessment across several challenges. These challenges are embedded in the curriculum, creating an student determined learning path with optimal flexibility in learning trajectories within a thematic Domain.

1.4 BUILDING BLOCKS FOR REFLECTION

This paragraph will briefly look at what it entails in practice for technee's to become critical consciousness-raising, autonomous, self-directed learners and critical thinkers. The Biomedical master where we are implementing this vision has three sub-tracks. For the demonstration of the model, we have chosen a hypothetical sub-track bio-medical physics. Imagine, for example, the following example of a Biomedical Challenge::

"High-tech devices often require expensive replacement parts. Due to the rugged environments of most developing countries, the devices fail frequently, and access to replacement parts is often difficult and expensive. Lack of financial resources, manufacturing equipment, and capacity to fabricate parts is non-existent."

What is the knowledge needed and what needs reflection upon?

Basic Knowledge

- Reflecting from different knowledge frames .e.g. Medical, Materials, Logistics, Legal, Economic
- Which methods and tools and knowledge are available to solve a problem?
- Epistemology of interdisciplinarity

The basic knowledge includes all the different disciplines represented in this challenge. One needs to know about high tech devices, materials, environmental, legal, cultural, political and societal impact. Possibly, the technee's need not know all of this, but they should know whom to contact. From the disciplinary perspectives, say high tech devices design and materials, one might reflect on the type of materials that could be used, design with circularity principles might be another one. However, from an environmental perspective, this might be a completely different disciplinary solution pattern. The critical question is; What is needed for this problem to be satisfactorily solved as a BME professional. (Level 1 of the Deliberate Professional)

In a reflection try out one of the piloting students stated:

"I think that oftentimes what I am lacking is a more profound interest in the fundamentals that underlie the creative process. If I want to be a biomaterials engineer, I need to find this topic interesting and learn more about it rather than just telling everybody how I find it prospective and interesting. My proactivity is often lacking in contrast to my soft skills."

Institutional Knowledge

- Reflect on the dimensions of future behaviour in profit/non-profit organisations and society you are working for, from different stakeholder perspectives?
- What does It all mean for my problem definition?

This next level, “Institutional Knowledge”, mainly addresses what contextual knowledge is. In a developing nation, should he/she work based on interpersonal trust? What is the system the client is doing his/her work in? Is there a system? How long are the devices used, what type of pollution is occurring, should the legal system change. Here, the knowledge focuses on contextual issues of the challenging environment in the developing nation and requires reflection on the tools and methods, ways of working, and society’s impact. (level 2 of the Deliberate professional)

Engineering Roles

- Reflect on: Whom do I want to be in this life, this story, what is my role, intention, stance, values with respect to this problem I’m working on.
- What do I want to keep/what do I want to change
- Behaviourial aspects creating Agency

The Engineering Roles level is focusing on what type of values ethical and in terms of sustainability should be adhered to, what is the role (leadership) one would like to demonstrate as an engineer, how to communicate and have critical thinking skills in this type of setting. Should we educate people, built a factory, import cheap devices? The reflection here focuses on “whom I want to be in this setting”, “whether I want to be in this situation?”, and “how I can act responsibly towards myself, the people, and the environment, while delivering an optimal product to provide medical support in the developing country. (level 3 of the Deliberate Professional)

To give an example from a pilot reflection session on the engineering roles:

“This assignment makes me think about the fact that during this course/specialization, I like to be more focused on the societal aspects than the technologies. I think maybe be since during my studies there is hardly room for issues like that. That is just not the focus of my study programme, so it makes sense.”

Challenges

- Professional Attitude/Deliberate Professional.
- Which Challenges (BME) do I want to engage with my knowledge, values, roles and the idea of impact I would like to have on the world
- Conscious performance of Engineering Profession

Finally, at the Challenge level, students should encounter different types of challenges such that they will be able to contribute to different knowledge systems such as industry, government, society, environment and personal knowledge [3]

Ideally, each challenge creates an authentic learner experience in which the different levels of

- Basic ((inter)disciplinary) knowledge,
- Institutional-Dimensional knowledge,
- Engineering Roles- Individual knowledge and
- Agency levels are addressed to become the Deliberate professional ultimately.

A professional who is aware of multiple agencies necessary for innovation, free will and the growth in different engineering roles across a wide variety of future contexts (level 4 deliberate professional)

1.5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper has shown the conceptual design of reflective engineering in Bio-medical Education for the future university. This proof of concept is a reflective journey within a first challenge-based course and will be tested and evaluated as a minimal viable product. After this 1st pilot, the conceptual design will be expanded to a framework for the entire master programme and related to the final attainment outcomes and future job prospects of BME master students.

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